

Synthesis of stress conditions along the Trüllikon borehole for the CITru project

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Executive summary

This report contributes to Phase 1 of the CO₂ pilot injection in Trüllikon (CITru) project and provides a state-of-knowledge review of in-situ stress conditions along the Trüllikon borehole (TRU1-1). The stress state is a key design input for deep injection, because it constrains the maximum bottom-hole pressure that can be applied without inducing unwanted formation destabilization or fracture propagation. In turn, for a given formation permeability and thickness, this pressure limit constrains the achievable injection rate. A robust stress estimate is therefore central to CO₂ injection planning and has direct implications for operational logistics as well as surface and subsurface infrastructure.

In-situ stress cannot be measured directly and requires integrating multiple lines of evidence, including dedicated stress-estimation tests such as hydraulic fracturing tests, together with more general information on rock behavior, in order to ensure a consistent and robust stress estimate. In this context, the data collected by Nagra is very comprehensive compared to data sets acquired on standard engineering projects. The measurement methods deployed and the analysis methods follow the state-of-the-art, so rather than reanalyzing this information, the objective here is to synthesize and extract the information relevant to the CITru project. In terms of integration, Nagra has conducted its work on a larger scale, encompassing data from multiple boreholes at the siting region level. Here, we propose integration at the borehole level, showing that while the stress field is well characterized overall, some local inconsistencies remain.

For the CITru project, the most relevant factors are the stress conditions in the reservoir formation (Schinznach Fm.) and in the caprock above it (Bänkerjoch Fm.). The best information is derived from hydraulic fracturing tests conducted in these formations. Analysis of these tests has made it possible to define the most probable ranges of values for the various components of the stress field. These results are as follows:

	Reservoir (Schinznach Formation)	Caprock (Bänkerjoch Formation)
Depth of the tests [m]	1093 to 1097	1051 to 1076
S_{hmin} magnitude [MPa]	17.4 to 19.1	22.0 to 25.2
S_{Hmax} magnitude [MPa]	22.7 to 25.9	29.1 to 33.2
S_v magnitude [MPa]	27.5	26.3 to 27.0
Maximum horizontal stress azimuth [°]		163°
Pore pressure P_p [MPa]	10.3	–

The stress regime is transitional between normal and strike-slip faulting ($S_{hmin} < S_{Hmax} \approx S_v$) in the Bänkerjoch Fm., suggesting a tendency toward strike-slip faulting, and normal faulting ($S_{hmin} < S_{Hmax} < S_v$) in the Schinznach Fm. Fracture propagation should be controlled by the S_{hmin} magnitude, and thus, taking 90% of the lower bound of the S_{hmin} range leads to a maximum allowable injection pressure of 15.7 MPa. This is a key parameter for the design of injection into the reservoir.

These results have been integrated by Nagra through comparison with data collected from other boreholes. Large-scale numerical stress models were calibrated using these data to provide a comprehensive and coherent picture of the stress state in the siting region. The models account for both gravitational

and tectonic loading of a layered elastic medium. Stress variability with depth arises from contrasts in the elastic properties of the individual layers (Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio). The calibrated models reasonably match the data available from the Trüllikon borehole; however, at this large scale, material properties are homogenized by formation, resulting in a smoothed stress profile along the borehole.

We complemented this work by constructing a borehole-scale stress model. The model is based on the same principles as the large-scale model, namely gravitational and tectonic loading of a layered elastic medium. However, by assuming a simplified local geometry with horizontal layers, the model can be solved analytically. This approach incorporates the detailed variability of material properties along the well without requiring homogenization or smoothing. Mechanical properties were derived from sonic log data calibrated against mechanical tests on core samples, with a depth resolution of approximately 15 cm. Similar to the [Nagra](#) large-scale model, our model was calibrated against stress estimates obtained from stress measurements. The resulting model provides a fine-scale estimate of the stress state along the Trüllikon borehole. We further verified the consistency of the model with observations of borehole failure using a borehole failure simulator. Within the uncertainty associated with borehole wall strength, the model is generally consistent with the observed borehole failures. However, some inconsistencies remain. In particular, the model fails to accurately reproduce the higher measured stresses in the caprock compared to the reservoir formation because the reservoir rock exhibits a higher stiffness than the caprock and, in our model, tends to attract stress under tectonic loading.

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Acronyms

BOs borehole breakouts. 16, 32, 34, 37, 41

CITru CO₂ pilot injection in Trüllikon. 3, 10, 37

DITFs drilling induced tensile fractures. 12, 16, 31, 32, 34, 37, 41

FMI formation microimager. 12, 16

GR gamma ray. 11

HDDP heavy-duty double packer. 18

HFs hydraulic fractures. 16

ISIP instantaneous shut-in pressure. 15

ISRM International Society for Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering. 12

JO Jura Ost. 16, 20

MEM mechanical earth model. 10, 25, 31, 33, 34, 36, 37, 40

MHF micro-hydraulic fracturing. 11, 12, 40

Nagra National Cooperative for the Disposal of Radioactive Waste. 3–5, 10–25, 32, 35, 37, 41

NL Nördlich Lägern. 16, 20

SQRT square-root of shut-in time. 15

SRT step-rate test. 15

TBO deep borehole drilling campaign. 10, 34

TRX triaxial deformation. 27, 28, 40

UBI ultrasonic borehole imager. 12, 16

UCS unconfined compressive strength. 25–29, 32, 34, 40

ZNO Zürich Nordost. 11, 16, 20

Nomenclature

α	Coefficient of linear thermal expansion [1/°C]
β	Effective stress coefficient [-]
σ	Effective stress tensor [MPa]
\mathbf{S}	Total stress tensor [MPa]
ΔT	Temperature change [°C]
δ_{ij}	Kronecker delta [-]
ν	Poisson's ratio [-]
ω	Breakout angular opening also called width [°]
ψ	Internal friction angle [°]
ρ	Rock density [kg/m ³]
σ_c	Uniaxial compressive strength [MPa]
σ_T	Tensile strength [MPa]
θ	Polar angle around the borehole [°]
θ_{BO}	Breakout orientation relative to borehole highside [°]
ε_{\max}	Maximum horizontal strain [-]
ε_{\min}	Minimum horizontal strain [-]
a	Borehole radius [m]
c	Rock cohesion [MPa]
C_o	Uniaxial compressive strength [MPa]
E	Young's modulus [GPa]
e	Breakout extent also called depth of failure [mm]
P_p	Pore pressure [MPa]
P_w	Borehole fluid pressure [MPa]

Nomenclature

q	Mohr–Coulomb material constant [-]
r	Radial distance from borehole center [m]
S_1	Greatest principal stress [MPa]
S_2	Intermediate principal stress [MPa]
S_3	Least principal stress [MPa]
S_{Hmax}	Maximum horizontal stress [MPa]
S_{hmin}	Minimum horizontal stress [MPa]
S_v	Vertical/Overburden stress [MPa]
V_p	Compressional (P-wave) seismic velocity [m/s]
V_s	Shear (S-wave) seismic velocity [m/s]

1. Introduction

The planned CO₂ injection project in Trüllikon (CITru) is a pilot and demonstration initiative focused on investigating and testing the injection of CO₂ into the Swiss subsurface. It is the first project of its kind in Switzerland to explore geological CO₂ storage as part of broader efforts toward achieving a net-zero emissions future. The project aims at using the legacy borehole Trüllikon drilled by the **National Cooperative for the Disposal of Radioactive Waste (Nagra)** in order to access the Upper Muschelkalk limestones and test the possibility of injecting CO₂ into this formation. The CITru project is phased. This work is part of Phase 1, which consists mostly of desk-based analyses of existing data to determine the key parameters for a possible injection in the Trüllikon borehole. It will be followed by Phase 2 (borehole equipment and initial injection tests) and Phase 3 (larger scale CO₂ injection).

The in-situ stress regime is a fundamental design parameter for deep injection projects, as it defines the maximum bottom-hole pressure that can be applied without causing undesirable destabilization of the formation or growth of fractures. For a given reservoir permeability and thickness, this pressure threshold directly limits the achievable injection rate. Consequently, reliable stress characterization is essential for planning CO₂ injection, influencing operational logistics, as well as the design of surface and subsurface infrastructure. Furthermore, the stress state is a critical input for modeling reservoir behavior (e.g., Gunatilake et al., 2025) and for assessing seismic risk (e.g., Schultz et al., 2024).

1.1. Report scope and structure

The scope of this report is to document relevant information concerning the state of stress along the Trüllikon borehole. When this synthesis work was started, Nagra was still working on a compilation report on the stress state along the boreholes drilled as part of their **deep borehole drilling campaign (TBO)**. The relevant data were dispersed across various sources, and we made a specific effort to trace the sources of information (see sources of information in Appendix A.1). In June 2025, the report NAB 24-19 from Nagra was released, which provided a more solid basis to discuss the stress along the Trüllikon borehole. This report is the main source for this synthesis.

Our report is organized into two main parts. In Section 2, we synthesize the key stress information relevant for the CITru project. One key parameter is the least principal stress magnitude, as it constrains the maximum injection pressure that can be used to inject CO₂ in the subsurface. In this section, we present the relevant information concisely so that others can refer to it.

In Section 3, we go beyond reporting and synthesizing published values by integrating all relevant data in a local 1D **mechanical earth model (MEM)** for the Trüllikon borehole. This exercise aims to build confidence and to create a basis for integrating future stress relevant data that may be collected as part of the CITru project.

2. Summary of **Nagra** stress measurements

Nagra performed a series of stress measurements in the Trüllikon borehole (TRU1-1) using advanced hydraulic fracturing techniques (mini-frac combined with sleeve fracturing and sleeve reopening). In this section, we focus on synthesizing these direct stress measurements at the reservoir level and in adjacent formations (caprock). A first preliminary quicklook analysis of these mini-frac tests was published in report NAB 20-09 (RD3 in Table 5). A much more detailed analysis from nine boreholes in three siting regions in northern Switzerland, including 3-D geomechanical modeling, was published in NAB 24-19 (RD6 in Table 5). The Trüllikon borehole is one of three boreholes in the Zürich Nordost (ZNO) siting region.

2.1. Stress measurements in the Trüllikon borehole

Mini-frac tests, also referred to as **micro-hydraulic fracturing (MHF)** tests, are hydraulic injection tests in a sealed-off interval of a borehole. The interval has a length of approximately 1 m and is sealed above and below by packers measuring around 0.5 m in length. The mini-frac test involves sequential stages of fluid injection and withdrawal that are used to verify hydraulic isolation, confirm fracture initiation, and ensure that the fracture extends sufficiently to sample the far-field stress, i.e., the stress field unaffected by the presence of the borehole itself. Since hydraulic fractures propagate perpendicular to the least principal stress (S_3) direction in an isotropic and homogeneous (i.e., non-fractured) rock volume (Hubbert & Willis, 1957), mini-frac tests provide a good estimate of the stress magnitude and orientation.

A total of 28 mini-frac tests, of which 22 were considered successful, were attempted in the Trüllikon borehole by the wireline logging company Schlumberger (SLB). The tests extend from the Felsenkalke + Massenkalk unit (474 m) down to the Weitenau Fm. (1260 m). Tests were classified as unsuccessful when no formation breakdown was achieved or when a high-pressure seal could not be maintained. All other tests in which a closure stress could be estimated were considered successful.

The mini-frac test procedure is described in detail in the two *Nagra* NAB reports (RD3 and RD6 in Table 5) and in Desroches et al. (2023). It is reproduced briefly in the following. While a general testing procedure was applied for all test intervals, individual steps were adjusted in real time to optimize pressure records for closure stress estimation. Consequently, the number and type of steps varied between tests. Each mini-frac test typically included the following steps: depth correlation using **GR** logging, sleeve fracturing when no pre-existing fracture existed in the interval, packer inflation and leak-off testing to verify seal integrity, and a breakdown cycle to propagate the hydraulic fracture. This was followed by multiple reopening cycles consisting of injection, to propagate the fracture, and shut-in. A reopening cycle can also be a step-rate test or slamback/rebound test. Finally, a sleeve reopening with the packer was performed to detect and reactivate the previously created fractures.

Fig. 1 shows how the tool string is moved during the succession of sleeve fracturing, mini-frac test, and sleeve reopening. Sleeve fracturing was conducted to focus the test at the desired depth by creating vertical starter fractures. As a result, the subsequent breakdown cycle corresponds to fracture reopening rather than initial fracture creation (breakdown).

2. Summary of Nagra stress measurements

Figure 1: Test protocol of the mini-frac (MHF) tests. The tool string is moved between steps 1 and 2 to align the midpoint of the straddle-packer interval with the single-packer position. Between steps 2 and 3, the tool is moved back so that the single packer returns to its original depth. Reproduced from Desroches et al. (2023).

The procedure used differs from the **ISRM** standard (Haimson & Cornet, 2003). The core of the test, i.e., the fracture reopening and propagation cycles (2. in Fig. 1), is the same. However, the fracture initiation and final reopening differ, as they are performed using a packer sleeve in the Trüllikon tests. This methodology has two main advantages. First, fracture initiation is better controlled. In the standard procedure, the fracture most often initiates below the packers or at the interface between packer and interval, because packer pressure has to be maintained higher than interval pressure to ensure proper sealing. With the proposed procedure, the fracture initiates below a packer (sleeve) in a controlled manner. The second advantage is that reopening with a sleeve (3. in Fig. 1) provides a potentially more robust means of estimating the maximum horizontal stress. When reopening with a fluid, as in the standard procedure, there is always an ambiguity regarding whether fluid pressure has diffused into the fracture prior to its reopening. With the sleeve reopening approach, this ambiguity is removed, because the sleeve contains the pressure and no fluid pressure can diffuse into the fracture. The main challenge associated with sleeve-based fracture initiation and reopening is the accurate identification of the initiation or reopening pressure from packer pressure and volume records. This requires good knowledge of the compliance of the equipment used to perform the tests.

Following the mini-frac tests, the induced fractures were mapped using ultrasonic borehole imager (**UBI**) and formation microimager (**FMI**) logs. To distinguish hydraulic fractures from pre-existing fractures and DITFs, logging was performed both before and after the mini-frac tests.

2.2. Estimation of the least principal stress magnitude

The estimation of the least principal stress magnitude (S_3) is based on pressure transient analysis to identify the fluid pressure at which the fracture opens and closes. These pressures represent the normal stress acting on the fracture surface, providing an estimate of the far-field S_3 magnitude. Because the observed hydraulic fractures are predominantly vertical, S_3 is interpreted as the minimum horizontal stress (S_{hmin}) at Trüllikon, consistent with a strike-slip or normal faulting stress regime.

Various methods and diagnostic plots exist to estimate the S_3 magnitude from fracture reopening, closure, or fracture propagation during step-rate tests. Bröker and Ma (2022) and Desroches et al. (2023) give an overview of the different methods. It is widely accepted that fracture closure pressure provides the most reliable estimate of the S_3 magnitude (Guglielmi et al., 2023; McClure et al., 2016; Schmitt & Haimson, 2017). Fracture closure is a continuous process, partly controlled by fracture roughness and varying asperity contact area. This implies that the fracture closes over a time and pressure range. Thus, defining a closure range is more appropriate than defining a single closure value. In the *Nagra* reports, several methods are combined to give ranges of closure stress as S_3 magnitude estimates. It was ensured that the test continued until convergence was observed from one cycle to the next (Fig. 2). This confirms that the fracture has propagated sufficiently into the formation to sample the far-field stress.

Two closure-stress ranges were defined for each test: a wide range bounded by the lowest and highest expected values and a narrower range bounded by the lower and upper values, in which the true closure value most likely lies. These four bounds are not necessarily all different and may coincide, e.g., the lowest and lower bound might be the same. After comparing the estimated closure ranges to the estimated vertical stress (S_v) from integrated density logs and checking that the created fractures are (sub-)vertical, 19 of the 22 mini-frac tests in the Trüllikon borehole were assigned to represent the S_{hmin} magnitude. Two more tests were assigned to potentially represent S_{hmin} due to unclear or slanted fracture traces.

Table 1 summarizes the estimated S_{hmin} magnitudes. In the caprock (Bänkerjoch), two closely spaced test intervals estimate that S_{hmin} is likely between 22.33 and 24.41 MPa. The larger range of these two tests (lowest to highest bound) is 21.96 to 25.17 MPa. The tests are located in the middle of the Bänkerjoch Fm., characterized by cyclic successions of anhydrite and claystone. A third mini-frac test closer to the base of the Bänkerjoch, where massive anhydrite occurs, yields higher S_{hmin} magnitudes. Both S_{hmin} ranges for this test are the same, ranging from 28.20 to 28.70 MPa. The slanted fracture trace at the borehole wall in this test interval may indicate that the direction of maximum tensile stress is not aligned with the borehole axis or reflect a near-wellbore failure mechanism involving mixed-mode initiation, which may lead to an overestimation of the minimum horizontal stress magnitude.

In the reservoir dolostone (Stamberg Member in the Schinznach Fm.), two closely spaced mini-frac tests give comparable S_{hmin} magnitude ranges, even though the upper test has an unclear fracture trace. In both test intervals, the most likely S_{hmin} range coincides with the maximum estimated range (lowest to highest bound). Overall, the likely magnitude of S_{hmin} ranges from 17.43 to 19.14 MPa. Fig. 2 shows the reconciliation plots for the two test intervals, demonstrating that the different estimates of S_{hmin} converge with progressing cycle number.

2. Summary of Nagra stress measurements

Table 1: Closure stress and stress ratio estimates from mini-frac tests in the Trüllikon borehole. Modified after RD6.

Formation name	Successful test depth [m]	$S_{hmin,max} - S_{hmin,min}$ [MPa]	Closure stress [MPa]			Highest bound	Notes on comparing pre- and post-mini-frac images		Stress component
			Lowest bound	Lower bound	Upper bound		min	max	
Bänkerjoch	1051.55	1.04	21.96	22.33	23.37	25.17	Possible single wing new fracture, faint traces, same azimuth as station below	S_{hmin}	
Bänkerjoch	1053.6	0.37	22.90	24.05	24.41	24.41	New bi-wing fracture	S_{hmin}	
Bänkerjoch	1076.2	0.50	28.20	28.20	28.70	28.70	Slanted fracture	$S_{hmin}?$	
Schinznach	1093.1	0.97	18.17	18.17	19.14	19.14	Unclear	$S_{hmin}?$	
Schinznach	1097.32	0.70	17.43	17.43	18.14	18.14	Clear new single-wing fracture	S_{hmin}	

Formation name	Successful test depth [m]	S_{Hmax}/S_{hmin} [-]		S_{Hmax} [MPa]	
		min	max	min	max
Bänkerjoch	1051.55	-	-	-	-
Bänkerjoch	1053.6	1.21	1.36	29.1	33.2
Bänkerjoch	1076.2	-	-	-	-
Schinznach	1093.1	-	-	-	-
Schinznach	1097.32	1.3	1.43	22.7	25.9

2. Summary of Nagra stress measurements

Figure 2: Reconciliation plots for the two mini-frac tests in the Schinznach Fm., displaying closure stress estimates for each consecutive cycle. ISIP = instantaneous shut-in pressure, SQRT = square-root of shut-in time, SRT = step-rate test. Figures from Jean Desroches (personal communication).

2.3. Estimation of other stress parameters

2.3.1. Maximum horizontal stress magnitude

The maximum horizontal stress magnitude, which can correspond either to the intermediate principal stress (S_2) or the greatest principal stress (S_1) depending on the tectonic stress regime, was estimated using sleeve reopening tests (Fig. 1). The methodology is described in detail in RD6, Desroches and Kurkjian (1999), and Wileveau et al. (2007). Briefly, the reopening pressure of the fracture is estimated from packer pressure versus volume plots. This sleeve reopening pressure is then used to calculate the S_{Hmax} magnitude, incorporating the estimated range of S_{hmin} (using the lower and upper bound) magnitudes and pressure inside the fracture. The pressure inside the fracture is unknown and was estimated to lie between the hydrostatic mud pressure and an extrapolated upper bound from the mini-frac shut-in behavior of the last cycle. Additionally, correction factors for the stiffness of the packer membrane and the geometric deviation from plane strain assumptions were taken into account in the S_{Hmax} magnitude calculation.

In 9 of the mini-frac test intervals along the Trüllikon borehole, the S_{Hmax} magnitude could be estimated. Most other intervals were excluded from the analysis either because the fracture trace at the borehole wall was not subvertical, bi-wing and 180 degrees apart, or because no sleeve reopening pressure could be estimated. The results for the caprock (Bänkerjoch) and reservoir (Schinznach) are given in Table 1. In the caprock, S_{Hmax} magnitudes range from 29.1 to 33.2 MPa, whereas in the reservoir they are lower, with values between 22.7 and 25.9 MPa.

2. Summary of Nagra stress measurements

2.3.2. Stress orientation

The stress orientation in the Trüllikon borehole was analysed based on borehole breakouts (BOs), drilling induced tensile fractures (DITFs), and the hydraulic fractures (HFs) created by the mini-frac tests. Fig. 3a shows the observed borehole failures along the borehole trajectory. The failure data reveal two distinct orientation subsets (Fig. 3b): the first subset has an orientation of 145° and occurs above 608 m TVD inside the Malm and below 1212 m TVD (below the evaporitic Zeglingen Fm.). The second subset has an orientation of 175° and occurs in the rest of the Mesozoic sediments. Table 2 gives an overview of the mean S_{Hmax} orientation estimated from the different borehole failure data. DITF subsets I and III correspond to shallow and deep depth intervals along the borehole that exhibit stress orientations deviating from those observed in the rest of the borehole based on BOs, DITF subset II, and HFs.

Table 2: Summary of borehole stress orientation data along the Trüllikon borehole. Modified after RD6. FMI = formation microimager, UBI = ultrasonic borehole imager

Type	Log/test	S_{Hmax} orientation [°]	SD [°]	n	Total length [m]	Depth range MD [m]
BOs	FMI/UBI	156	9.0	66	34.8	674–1148
DITFs	FMI	151	19.0	74	133.5	520–1291
DITFs subset I	FMI	143	9.0	19	52.5	520–602
DITFs subset II	FMI	173	9.0	34	47.5	614–1152
DITFs subset III	FMI	134	9.0	21	33.5	1212–1291
HFs	mini-fracs	160	12.9	16	–	515–1054

The mean S_{Hmax} orientation in the Mesozoic sediments, based on borehole data from 9 boreholes in the regions Jura Ost (JO), Nördlich Lägern (NL), and Zürich Nordost (ZNO), is 166° N with a standard deviation of $\pm 12^\circ$. The Trüllikon borehole is the only exception to the otherwise consistent stress orientation pattern, suggesting a stress rotation with depth. The rotation within the Malm is interpreted as a local effect related to a fault zone. In contrast, the deeper rotation across the Zeglingen Fm. has been documented in other boreholes in the region and is considered evidence of mechanical decoupling. This decoupling may affect the south-eastern part of the ZNO siting region, but does not appear to affect the JO and NL siting regions, which are located north of the Jura Main Thrust.

In the reservoir (Schinznach Fm.) and caprock (Bänkerjoch Fm.) along the Trüllikon borehole, the best estimate of the S_{Hmax} orientation was derived from the circular average of the BOs and DITFs orientations. The average is 150° in the Bänkerjoch Fm. and 166° in the Schinznach Fm. Taken together over both formations, the circular average is 163° , which is coherent with the overall orientation based on data from the 9 boreholes in the region and represents our best estimate of the S_{Hmax} orientation in the reservoir and caprock in Trüllikon.

The S_{Hmax} orientation derived from borehole failure data is consistent with those from earthquake focal mechanisms. The latter yield a mean S_{Hmax} orientation of approximately 159° N $\pm 22^\circ$ from basement earthquakes at depths of 2–22 km. However, the focal-mechanism data exhibit substantially greater scatter due to their higher inherent uncertainty.

2. Summary of Nagra stress measurements

(a) Observed borehole failure along the borehole trajectory.

(b) Rose diagrams illustrating the orientations of borehole failures.

Figure 3: Summary of borehole failures observed in the Trüllikon borehole. Figure reproduced from RD6.

2. Summary of *Nagra* stress measurements

2.3.3. Vertical stress

The vertical stress (S_v) was calculated by the integration of the density log (RD3, Appendix A).

2.3.4. Pore pressure

In order to be exhaustive, an estimate of the in-situ pore pressure is also part of a complete stress characterization, although it overlaps with hydraulic testing and reservoir characterization.

Pore pressures were determined from nine hydraulic packer tests using a single- or heavy-duty double packer (HDDP) system. The tests isolated specific geological formations with interval length between 11.4 m and 44.3 m. Pressure responses measured during the packer tests were used to estimate static formation/pore pressures (Table 3). These pore pressure estimates, including uncertainty ranges, were compiled and interpreted by the field contractor and reported in RD4 (see Table 5).

Table 3: Pore pressures along Trüllikon borehole estimated by hydraulic packer testing. Modified after RD6.

Test name	Test interval [m bgl]		Interval length [m]	Pore pressure P_s [MPa]			Hydraulic model
	From	To		Lowest	Best	Highest	
TRU1-1-MAL1	589.00	600.38	11.38	5.213	5.247	5.512	Radial-composite w. changing wellbore storage
TRU1-1-BDO1	782.30	805.30	23.00	7.817	7.999	8.289	Homogeneous with skin
TRU1-1-BDO2	806.50	822.20	15.70	7.310	7.706	7.714	Homogeneous with skin
TRU1-1-OPA2	829.00	854.00	25.00	11.993	12.710	14.109	Homogeneous with skin
TRU1-1-OPA3	868.50	887.45	18.95	10.446	11.647	12.753	Two zones radial composite
TRU1-1-LIA2	923.72	944.50	20.78	11.528	13.041	14.309	Two zones radial composite
TRU1-1-LIA1	944.50	965.28	20.78	9.924	11.260	12.384	Three zones radial composite
TRU1-1-KEU1	990.70	1035.00	44.30	9.137	9.143	9.157	Homogeneous with time varying skin
TRU1-1-MUK1	1085.30	1110.30	25.00	10.251	10.255	10.261	Homogeneous with skin

2.4. Comparison of Trüllikon to other boreholes

The estimated S_{hmin} magnitudes in the Trüllikon borehole in the Schinznach and Bänkerjoch formations agree with the values from the other boreholes of the *Nagra* deep borehole campaign (Fig. 4). To facilitate comparison between locations where the formation depths differ, the S_{hmin} are normalized by the depth, thus generating stress gradients in [MPa/km]. For the Schinznach Fm., the S_{hmin} gradient appears to be homogeneous within and across siting regions. In the Bänkerjoch Fm., a bimodal distribution of S_{hmin} is observed. Investigations revealed a strong correlation between variations in S_{hmin} gradient and the amount of anhydrite, and consequently stiffness, in the tested interval. A high anhydrite content leads to a greater stiffness and, therefore, higher S_{hmin} gradients. This is shown in Fig. 5 in a conceptual model that shows how tectonic loading leads to high S_{hmin} magnitudes in stiffer limestone formations, equivalent to stiffer anhydrite, compared to softer claystones. However, under low tectonic loading, claystone layers can exhibit a higher S_{hmin} gradient due to their higher Poisson's ratio. This behavior is observed in the limestone and claystone formations of the Malm, where the Felsenkalke + Massenkalk and Villigen formations represent stiffer limestones, while the Schwarzbach and Wildegg formations are softer claystones that have a higher S_{hmin} gradient.

Test intervals with higher S_{hmin} gradients generally also exhibit higher S_{Hmax} gradients, reflected in an overall increase in the S_{Hmax}/S_{hmin} ratio with increasing S_{hmin} gradient across all siting regions. The observed relationship indicates that stiffness likely affects both horizontal stress magnitudes.

2. Summary of Nagra stress measurements

Figure 4: Overview of S_{hmin} gradients by lithology from boreholes in the siting regions Zürich Nordost (ZNO), Nördlich Lägern (NL), and Jura Ost (JO). The Trüllikon borehole is in the ZNO region. Horizontal bars indicate gradient ranges derived from mini-frac tests, while gray vertical bars show median bounds for each lithology. Bimodal gradients in the Bänkerjoch Fm. reflect alternating stiff and weak layers. Figure reproduced from RD6.

2. Summary of Nagra stress measurements

Figure 5: Conceptual model illustrating the effect of tectonic loading on S_{hmin} magnitudes in a limestone–claystone stratigraphic column. Left panel: Under purely gravitational loading, S_{hmin} is higher in claystones than in limestones due to the higher Poisson’s ratio of the claystone ($\nu_2 > \nu_1$). Middle panel: With the addition of tectonic loading, S_{hmin} increases more strongly in limestone because of its higher Young’s modulus ($E_1 > E_2$). Right panel: At higher levels of tectonic loading, shallow limestone units may develop S_{hmin} magnitudes exceeding the vertical stress S_v . Figure reproduced from RD6.

2.5. Stress profile along Trüllikon borehole

The three principal stress magnitudes estimated from the mini-frac tests (S_{hmin} , S_{Hmax}) and from integrating the density logs (S_v) are shown in Fig. 6. Additionally, the results of 3D geomechanical-numerical models are shown. The models are explained in detail in RD6. They incorporate gravitational volume forces and tectonic stresses (surface forces) to model the stresses. The model is calibrated by varying the tectonic forces, in the form of lateral displacement boundary conditions, so that the model best fits the mini-frac results.

The distribution of elastic properties has been determined for each formation using the results of core testing and petrophysical log analysis (RD7 in Table 5). For example, for the Young’s modulus (or E-modulus; representing the stiffness), the model uses the median (P50) value from the cumulative density function for each formation. Fig. 7 shows the Young’s modulus distribution for each formation along the Trüllikon borehole. The Schinznach Fm. is stiffer than the overlying Bänkerjoch. The

2. Summary of Nagra stress measurements

Figure 6: Stress magnitudes and model results along the Trüllikon borehole. Solid lines show stress components from the best-fit model using median (P50) rock stiffness values, while dashed lines represent results obtained using stiffness values estimated from sonic logs at each mini-frac interval (spanning the P05–P95 range). Figure reproduced from RD6.

Bänkerjoch Fm. shows a greater variability in Young’s modulus due to competent/stiff anhydrite-rich layers, leading to a relatively high P95 value.

Overall, the model fit shown in Fig. 6 is broadly consistent with the measured stress magnitudes. However, S_{hmin} is underestimated in the Klettgau and Bänkerjoch formations. This discrepancy likely arises because the model applies median (P50) stiffness values uniformly across each formation, whereas mini-frac tests probe meter-scale intervals where local stiffness can differ substantially from the median. To evaluate whether this effect explains the mismatch, sonic log data were used to estimate the stiffness value from the distribution that best represents each mini-frac station. The model results, which

2. Summary of *Nagra* stress measurements

incorporate these station-specific stiffness values, are shown by the dashed lines in S_{hmin} . They exhibit a markedly improved fit to the stress magnitude data. These results demonstrate that rock stiffness is the key factor controlling the in-situ stress field.

Since laboratory-derived rock stiffness values were not measured directly at the mini-frac test locations and the formations show variation in elastic moduli, multiple models were run to assess if the estimated stress magnitudes are representative of a larger rock volume. Fig. 7 shows the bandwidth of modeled stress magnitudes (median, P25-P75, and P05-P95) using the P05 – P95 distributions of rock stiffness in each formation. The competent layers of the Klettgau and Bänkerjoch formations exhibit greater stress variability, expressed as a wider stress bandwidth, than the weaker, clay-rich formations. This increased variability reflects the larger spread in rock stiffness within the stiff units, particularly their high P95 stiffness values. Consequently, these competent layers tend to shield the adjacent weaker formations, which also have a narrower P05–P95 stiffness distribution.

Note also that smoothing along the profile and across formations arises from the 3D finite element approach used to derive this model. In order to run tractable full 3D models, the element size at the local level needs to be a compromise. The element type (e.g., 2nd-order elements) also influences how the interpolation between layers is performed. In Fig. 7, the abrupt changes in E-moduli with depth are not reflected in the relatively smooth stress magnitude profiles. This inconsistency is likely the result of model resolution and elemental smoothing. To obtain a more detailed profile along the Trüllikon borehole, we derived a 1D mechanical earth model (see Section 3) based on simpler analytical approaches, complementary to the full-blown 3D stress model presented in RD6 (see Table 5).

2. Summary of Nagra stress measurements

Figure 7: Range of modeled stress magnitudes along the Trüllikon borehole. Median values are shown by bold lines, with dark grey and light grey shading indicating the P25–P75 and P05–P95 ranges, respectively. Horizontal red and blue lines denote stress magnitudes measured by mini-frac tests. Left panel: P05–P95 distribution of modeled S_{hmin} magnitudes. Middle panel: P05–P95 rock stiffness distribution (Young’s modulus). Right panel: P05–P95 distribution of modeled S_{Hmax} magnitudes. Figure reproduced from RD6.

3. Trüllikon local stress model

A comprehensive dataset is available for the Trüllikon borehole and has been released by Nagra. In addition to state-of-the-art stress measurement data, the dataset includes lithostratigraphic information, mechanical testing results from core samples, and a complete suite of borehole logging data. This breadth of information provides the opportunity to integrate the datasets and assess the internal consistency of the collected geomechanical data. In the petroleum literature, such data integration is commonly referred to as a **mechanical earth model (MEM)**. This type of integration and coherency assessment is an integral part of strategies for characterizing the stress conditions at sites (Stephanson & Zang, 2012). Here, it is applied as a complementary approach to the regional-scale integration performed by Nagra, allowing for a fine-scale characterization of the stress state along the Trüllikon borehole.

3.1. Compilation of available data

Our 1D geomechanical model takes advantage of many of the measured geomechanical and petrophysical parameters in the Trüllikon borehole. The data sources are listed in Appendix A. In the following, we briefly list all input parameters:

- **Lithological units and boundaries** estimated from cores and logging.
- **Borehole trajectory** measured by logging tools.
- **Stress magnitudes** derived from mini-frac tests (S_{hmin} , S_{Hmax}) and by integrating the density log (S_v).
- **Pore pressure** estimated from hydraulic tests using single or double-packer systems.
- **Geomechanical rock properties** (Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, UCS) measured by laboratory tests.
- **Density and sonic velocities** (V_p , V_s) from logging.

3.2. Stress model and parameter adjustments

3.2.1. Computation of horizontal stresses

Our 1D geomechanical model predicts the horizontal stresses at any depth by taking into account the volume forces from gravity and surface forces from lateral displacements (Savage et al., 1992), which correspond to tectonic stresses (Eq. 1). The formulation assumes linear elastic, isotropic behavior, providing a first-order estimate of the in-situ stress distribution. Given the rock's density and elastic properties estimated and measured by logs and laboratory tests, the only free parameters are the lateral displacement boundary conditions (ε_{max} and ε_{min}), which correspond conceptually to the tectonic strains and must be calibrated to fit the estimated stress magnitude data from mini-frac tests.

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$$\begin{aligned} S_{hmin} &= \frac{\nu}{1-\nu} S_v + \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} (\varepsilon_{min} + \nu \varepsilon_{max}) \\ S_{Hmax} &= \frac{\nu}{1-\nu} S_v + \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} (\varepsilon_{max} + \nu \varepsilon_{min}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The stress model was calibrated by optimizing the two horizontal displacement parameters ε_{max} and ε_{min} using a least-squares approach, with the aim of minimizing the discrepancy between the modeled and observed S_{hmin} magnitudes. We used the lower and upper bound of the closure stress (Table 1) and defined the objective function so that no misfit is assigned as long as the modeled stress magnitude falls within the measured uncertainty bounds. To account for the uneven depth distribution and varying reliability of stress measurements, weighting was applied in the least-squares optimization. All measurements were assigned a default weight of 1. Measurements deeper than 950 m were given double weight in the objective function to compensate for the lower number of mini-frac tests in the deep interval (950–1250 m) compared to the shallow interval (500–950 m). The measurement at 843.6 m was interpreted as an HTPF test and was excluded from the optimization. Measurements at 1076.2 m and 1093.1 m were assigned half weight due to increased uncertainty associated with unclear or potentially slanted fracture traces.

3.2.2. Petrophysical relationships

To obtain continuous estimates for Poisson's ratio (ν) and Young's modulus (E), we calculated both from sonic velocity and the density log (ρ) using the standard relationships (e.g., Mari & Vergnault, 2018):

$$\nu = \frac{V_p^2 - 2V_s^2}{2(V_p^2 - V_s^2)} \quad (2)$$

$$E = \rho V_s^2 \left(\frac{3V_p^2 - 4V_s^2}{V_p^2 - V_s^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

In a similar manner, we fitted a site-specific relationship between UCS and sonic velocity, as described in the next section.

3.2.3. UCS vs. P-wave velocity

The **unconfined compressive strength (UCS)** is an important parameter to analyze the initiation and width of borehole breakouts. There were 51 UCS tests conducted on cylindrical test samples from the Trüllikon borehole core. The unconfined compressive peak strength (UCS) was derived from the peak axial load at which the test sample failed. The details of the tests are presented in RD5 (see Table 5).

To estimate the UCS at depths where no laboratory test was conducted, we developed a relationship between UCS and sonic P-wave velocity (V_p), which was recorded by sonic logging along most of the

3. Trüllikon local stress model

Figure 8: P-wave velocity (V_p) from the sonic logging (blue line) and laboratory TRX measurements (red squares) along the Trüllikon borehole.

borehole. We did not use sonic velocities measured on core in the laboratory. The main difference between the two methods is that in-situ measurements obtained with the logging tool are performed in the kHz frequency range, whereas laboratory measurements are conducted in the MHz range. Fig. 8 compares V_p from sonic logging with V_p measured on core samples in laboratory **triaxial deformation (TRX)** tests. The two datasets show good agreement in terms of overall trends, indicating that the logging data capture the large-scale elastic properties of the formation. However, in nearly all cases the P-wave velocities measured in the TRX tests are systematically higher than the corresponding sonic-log velocities (see also the square symbols in Fig. 9). This difference is attributed to frequency-dependent seismic dispersion. At ultrasonic frequencies wave-induced fluid-pressure equilibration in compliant pore space (e.g., microcracks or pores) is suppressed, resulting in a stiffer effective rock frame and higher measured velocities (Müller et al., 2010).

Fig. 9 shows a cross-plot of UCS and V_p that we used to identify a relationship for the Trüllikon borehole. The measurement points in the Bänkerjoch anhydrite and Schinznach dolostone are highlighted. We fitted a relationship between UCS and V_p using a power-law function of the form

$$UCS = a \left(\frac{V_p}{1000} \right)^b, \quad (4)$$

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Figure 9: Cross-plot of UCS and V_p with scatter points colored by lithology. Circles correspond to velocities from sonic logging and squares to velocities estimated from **TRX** tests within 1 m of the corresponding UCS tests. Samples from the Bänkerjoch and Schinznach formations are highlighted with a black edge. Three power laws were fitted to the data (Table 4).

where the parameters a and b were estimated by nonlinear least-squares regression using only the velocity data inferred from the sonic logs (circles in Fig. 9). Power-law relationships of this form are commonly reported in the literature (e.g., Jamshidi et al., 2018; Kılıç & Teymen, 2008). The resulting best-fit model defines the mid relationship between the variables. To quantify uncertainty, 95% functional confidence intervals were first computed for the fitted relationship. Power-law expressions were then fitted to the lower and upper confidence bounds to generate analytical formulas for the low and high trend curves. Table 4 lists the three estimated formulas.

Table 4: Fitted power-law formulas for UCS and V_p relationship.

Curve	Formula
Low	$UCS = 3.679 (V_p/1000)^{1.915}$
Mid	$UCS = 6.216 (V_p/1000)^{1.744}$
High	$UCS = 9.397 (V_p/1000)^{1.612}$

There are several data points at high velocities (>5800 m/s) and low UCS values (<80 MPa) that the relationship does not capture well. All of these were measured in the limestones of the Malm (Felsenkalke + Massenkalk, <600 m depth) and these tests were controlled by planes of relative weakness, e.g. healed fractures or stylolites. Therefore, these data points do not reflect the behavior of intact rock and cannot be reliably estimated from sonic velocity measurements alone.

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This approach for estimating UCS from V_p is common in the literature, and numerous empirical relationships have been proposed (e.g., Jamshidi et al., 2018, for a review). However, comparison of the published relationships reveals large discrepancies, particularly at higher velocities. Consequently, deriving site-specific relationships based on local data is likely to provide the most reliable estimates. Nevertheless, as shown in Fig. 9, substantial uncertainty remains even for the locally derived empirical relationship, despite the availability of an extensive dataset from the Trüllikon borehole. For example, at a velocity of 6000 m/s, the observed UCS values span more than 200 MPa, while the best-fit relationship with 95% confidence bounds covers a range of approximately 50 MPa. This level of uncertainty must be considered when using this strength estimate in the following section. Nevertheless, this approach represents the most rational method for deriving a continuous strength profile along a borehole.

3.2.4. Computation of borehole failure

The computation of borehole failure follows the approach presented by Dahrabou et al. (2022) and is performed in two main steps: (i) the computation of the stress state at the borehole wall, including the influence of the borehole itself, and (ii) the evaluation of failure using appropriate strength criteria. In our computation, linear elasticity is assumed.

The stress at the borehole wall can be computed using the so-called Kirsch solution (Kirsch, 1898), as presented for example in Schmitt et al. (2012). The computation consists of (1) expressing the stress tensor \mathbf{S}_{uvw} in a borehole-local reference frame $(\vec{u}, \vec{v}, \vec{w})$, with \vec{u} and \vec{v} in the plane normal to the borehole and \vec{w} aligned with the borehole axis; and (2) computing the stress around the excavated borehole in a cylindrical coordinate system $(\vec{r}, \vec{\theta}, \vec{w})$, with the total stress tensor given as a function of r (the radial distance from the borehole center) and θ ($\theta = 0^\circ$ points toward the borehole high side) as:

$$\mathbf{S}_{r\theta w} = \begin{pmatrix} S_{rr} & S_{r\theta} & S_{rw} \\ S_{\theta r} & S_{\theta\theta} & S_{\theta w} \\ S_{wr} & S_{w\theta} & S_{ww} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where:

$$S_{rr} = \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{r^2}\right) \left(\frac{S_u + S_v}{2}\right) + \left(1 + \frac{3a^4}{r^4} - \frac{4a^2}{r^2}\right) \left(\frac{S_u - S_v}{2}\right) \cos 2\theta + \left(1 + \frac{3a^4}{r^4} - \frac{4a^2}{r^2}\right) S_{uv} \sin 2\theta + \left(\frac{a^2}{r^2}\right) P_w \quad (6)$$

$$S_{\theta\theta} = \left(1 + \frac{a^2}{r^2}\right) \left(\frac{S_u + S_v}{2}\right) - \left(1 + \frac{3a^4}{r^4}\right) \left(\frac{S_u - S_v}{2}\right) \cos 2\theta - \left(1 + \frac{3a^4}{r^4}\right) S_{uv} \sin 2\theta - \left(\frac{a^2}{r^2}\right) P_w \quad (7)$$

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$$S_{ww} = S_z - 4\nu \frac{a^2}{r^2} \left(\frac{S_u - S_v}{2} \right) \cos 2\theta - 4\nu \frac{a^2}{r^2} S_{uv} \sin 2\theta \quad (8)$$

$$S_{r\theta} = - \left(1 - \frac{3a^4}{r^4} + \frac{2a^2}{r^2} \right) \left(\frac{S_u - S_v}{2} \right) \sin 2\theta + \left(1 - \frac{3a^4}{r^4} + \frac{2a^2}{r^2} \right) S_{uv} \cos 2\theta \quad (9)$$

$$S_{rw} = \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{r^2} \right) (S_{vw} \sin \theta + S_{uw} \cos \theta) \quad (10)$$

$$S_{\theta w} = \left(1 + \frac{a^2}{r^2} \right) (S_{vw} \cos \theta - S_{uw} \sin \theta) \quad (11)$$

with ν the Poisson's ratio and a the borehole radius. This solution includes an internal borehole fluid pressure P_w .

At the borehole wall ($r = a$) and considering a thermo-elastic stress component $S_{r,\theta,w}^{\Delta T}$ the solution reduces to:

$$S_{rr} = P_w + S_r^{\Delta T} \quad (12)$$

$$S_{\theta\theta} = S_u + S_v - 2(S_u - S_v) \cos(2\theta) - 4S_{uv} \sin(2\theta) - P_w + S_\theta^{\Delta T} \quad (13)$$

$$S_{ww} = S_z - 2\nu(S_u - S_v) \cos(2\theta) - 4\nu S_{uv} \sin(2\theta) + S_w^{\Delta T} \quad (14)$$

$$S_{r\theta} = S_{rw} = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$S_{\theta w} = 2[S_{vw} \cos(\theta) - S_{uw} \sin(\theta)] \quad (16)$$

With the thermo-elastic stress component for a temperature change ΔT (cooling negative, heating positive) and considering a coefficient of linear expansion α (Stephens & Voight, 1982):

$$S_r^{\Delta T} = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$S_\theta^\Delta = S_w^\Delta = \frac{\alpha E \Delta T}{1 - \nu} \quad (18)$$

The failure is then evaluated around the borehole wall considering the effective stress:

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$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{S} - \beta \delta_{ij} P_p \quad (19)$$

where P_p is the fluid pressure, and \boldsymbol{S} and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ are the total and effective stress tensors, respectively. $\beta \in [0, 1]$ is the coefficient in the effective stress law and is typically taken as $\beta = 1$, which implies that the pore pressure “penetrates” the rock and is therefore fully accounted for in the effective stress. Such behavior has been shown in laboratory experiments even for low-porosity rocks (Brace & Martin, 1968), although this remains a subject of discussion and a source of uncertainty. δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta, which applies pore pressure subtraction only to the isotropic components of \boldsymbol{S} .

The Mohr–Coulomb criterion is considered in effective principal stress space:

$$\sigma_1 \geq C_o + q\sigma_3 \quad (20)$$

where C_o is the uniaxial compressive strength of the rock, and q is a material constant. Both C_o and q can be related to the internal friction angle, ψ , and the cohesion, c through:

$$q = \tan \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\psi}{2} \right)^2 \quad (21)$$

$$C_o = \frac{2c \cos \psi}{1 - \sin \psi} \quad (22)$$

The computation of breakout width, ω , consists of evaluating the failure criteria (Eq. 20) at the borehole wall (i.e. $r = a, \forall \theta$) using the stresses calculated by the Kirsch closed-form solution. The arc, measured as the angle along which the failure criterion is met, provides an estimate of ω . The assumption behind such computation is that failure occurs at the cylindrical borehole wall spanning an initial maximum width, and then the breakouts progressively extend (deepen) but do not widen. It is therefore not necessary to simulate the progressive failure leading to the final breakout geometry. Although some modifications of breakout width with time have been reported in-situ (Azzola et al., 2019), the approach implemented in our methodology is widely accepted (Zoback et al., 2003). The point on the borehole circumference which is closest to failure in case of no failure or furthest beyond the failure line in case of failure is used to define the breakout orientation θ_{BO} given in the local borehole coordinate system.

The formation of DITFs is evaluated by checking whether the minimum effective stress at the borehole wall becomes tensile (tension taken as negative) and is more negative than $-T$, where T is the tensile strength.

3.3. Discussion of the results

Fig. 10 shows the final 1D MEM. The different plot panels show the following:

1. Lithostratigraphic column, including the formations, their constituent units, and corresponding geological periods.
2. Borehole trajectory with azimuth and deviation from vertical.

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3. Horizontal stress magnitudes, both estimated from mini-frac tests and modeled, vertical stress magnitude, and formation pore pressure together with hydrostatic fit.
4. S_{Hmax} orientation inferred from borehole breakouts (BOs) and drilling induced tensile fractures (DITFs).
5. Measured sonic velocities (V_p , V_s) from logging.
6. Measured density (ρ) from logging.
7. Poisson's ratio (ν) measured in laboratory tests and modeled from sonic velocities by Eq. 2.
8. Young's modulus (E) measured in laboratory tests and modeled from sonic velocities and the density log by Eq. 3.
9. UCS measured in laboratory tests and modeled using the three derived relationships with P-wave velocity in Table 4.
10. Mapped BOs and DITFs and their azimuth.
11. Mapped and modeled BOs width. As input for the UCS the three profiles in panel 9 are used.
12. Modeled occurrence of DITFs

The optimization of our stress model yielded an optimal minimum horizontal strain of $\varepsilon_{\min} = -2.22 \times 10^{-14}$ and a maximum horizontal strain of $\varepsilon_{\max} = 5.91 \times 10^{-4}$. The near-zero value of ε_{\min} indicates negligible extension in the minimum horizontal direction, while the positive ε_{\max} reflects compressional strain in the S_{Hmax} direction, which is close to N-S. The N-S compression is in the same magnitude as reported by Nagra in RD6, but they report a non-zero E-W extension. Our stress model fits well most of the measured S_{hmin} magnitudes. However, the S_{Hmax} magnitudes seem to be overestimated in some parts. For example, in the lower part of the Schinznach Fm., where a large V_s leads to a high modeled E (see Eq. 3), which in turn leads to high S_{Hmax} magnitude with >60 MPa in some depths. Large moduli and probably too large maximum horizontal stress magnitudes are also present in the upper Jurassic formations.

The modeled Poisson's ratio and Young's modulus agree well with many of the data measured in laboratory tests. However, large variations in both parameters were observed in some tests at the same depth, depending on sample orientation. Individual samples may be influenced by bedding, (healed) fractures, stylolites, and similar features, whereas the logging data sample a larger volume and therefore reflect average elastic properties. As previously mentioned, the modeled Young's modulus is very high in depth intervals with high V_s and exceeds the measured values by far, reaching more than 60 GPa and, in some sections, even more than 70 GPa. Most of these depth sections with high V_s and E correspond to limestone or dolostone lithologies of the Felsenkalke + Massenkalk, Villigen, Schinznach, and Zeglingen formations.

Also the UCS shows a large bandwidth for samples at the same depth. This is especially pronounced for tests in the Felsenkalke + Massenkalk and Schinznach formations, where core samples with very high UCS values around 240 MPa exist. Other samples in the Felsenkalke + Massenkalk Fm. failed at significantly lower UCS values due to planes of relative weakness, such as healed fractures or stylolites. Hence, our three derived UCS models do not capture all the measured values, but the majority of them.

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However, only the ‘low’ UCS– V_p relationship leads to the occurrence of borehole breakouts (BOs) in our model. The sparse observed BOs in the lower Malm and upper Dogger are not well captured in our model, as it mostly produces BOs across the whole Malm. This is likely due to unrealistically high S_{Hmax} magnitudes modeled for this section, which result from the high moduli values. In contrast, the absence of BOs in the Opalinus Clay and Staffelegg formations is well captured in our model. The main occurrence of BOs in the Klettgau, upper Bänkerjoch, and Schinznach formations is also reproduced. Overall, the model predicts BOs with a smaller width, but over larger depth intervals, and only for our lower strength profile.

Similarly to the BOs, the occurrence of drilling induced tensile fractures (DITFs) is mostly well captured by our model. DITFs appear primarily in the Malm, Schinznach, Dinkelberg, and Weitenau formations, as well as in the crystalline basement. While the model predicts DITFs over larger depth intervals than observed, it correctly reproduces their absence in the Opalinus Clay and some other Dogger formations.

3.3.1. Bänkerjoch and Schinznach formations

Fig. 11 highlights our 1D MEM results in the sections of the Bänkerjoch (caprock) and Schinznach (reservoir) formations. In general, the modeled minimum horizontal stress S_{hmin} is lower in the Bänkerjoch Fm. compared to the Schinznach Fm., except at the transition zone to the Schinznach, where a noticeable increase is observed. This is in contrast with mini-frac tests indicating that S_{hmin} in the Bänkerjoch is generally higher than in the Schinznach Fm. This may reflect a bimodal distribution of S_{hmin} in the Bänkerjoch Fm. (Section 2.4, Fig. 4), but in general S_{hmin} was found to be higher in the Bänkerjoch than in the Schinznach in all mini-frac tests of the TBO campaign. The maximum horizontal stress S_{Hmax} reasonably well matches the Bänkerjoch mini-frac test, but in the Schinznach Fm. S_{Hmax} is largely overestimated.

The Schinznach Fm. appears geologically relatively homogeneous, consisting predominantly of dolostones in the roughly upper half and limestones in the lower half (RD2 in Table 5). Within the section where mini-frac tests were performed, the formation shows limited lithological variability and no pronounced internal structuring. In this context, using Young’s modulus derived from the sonic log directly for stress-field computation seems appropriate. In contrast, the Bänkerjoch Fm. is significantly more heterogeneous. It comprises banded massive anhydrite (at the bottom of the formation) and cyclic sequences characterized by laminated anhydrites with thin claystone interbeds. The high-frequency alternation of stiff anhydrite layers and weaker, clay-rich intervals introduces significant vertical variability in elastic properties, potentially on a scale smaller than the sonic log’s resolution. This raises the question of whether the Young’s modulus derived from sonic logging truly represents the stiffness that controls the in-situ stress state at the meter scale. An additional limitation for the Bänkerjoch Fm. is that our 1D MEM assumes no depth coupling, meaning each depth point is treated as mechanically independent, with horizontal stresses calculated locally from elastic properties, without enforcing mechanical interaction or strain compatibility between adjacent layers. However, in strongly laminated formations with large stiffness contrasts, this assumption may not accurately reflect the true stress distribution.

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According to the conceptual model of limestone–claystone successions of Nagra (Section 2.4, Fig. 5), claystones have a higher S_{hmin} gradient under low tectonic loading, as their Poisson’s ratio is larger than that of limestones. In our model, Poisson’s ratio is fairly stable in the Bänkerjoch and Schinznach formations. The higher stress in the Schinznach Fm. in our model can be explained by the higher stiffness (expressed by a higher E) compared to the Bänkerjoch Fm., due to the higher measured velocities, especially V_s . This relationship is particularly noticeable in the pronounced increase in S_{hmin} , as well as in V_p , V_s , and E , within the Schinznach Fm. at 1119 m. This corresponds to the transition from dolostone at the top to limestone below.

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Figure 11: 1D MEM of the Trüllikon borehole. Zoom into the Bänkeroch and Schinznach formations, which are intended to serve as a caprock and reservoir, respectively. Further information is given in the text.

4. Synthesis and outlook

The state-of-the-art data collected by Nagra in the Trüllikon borehole provide a robust stress characterization of the site and a solid basis for designing CO₂ injections in this well. This dataset also allows for a complete integration of observations in a 1D MEM. This 1D MEM for the Trüllikon borehole is developed by integrating borehole failure, hydraulic fracturing stress measurements, laboratory rock-mechanical tests, and wireline logs. The model reproduces most measured S_{hmin} magnitudes and captures the first-order distribution of BOs and DITFs, including their general absence in the Opalinus Clay and Staffelegg formations. The main mismatch is an overestimation of S_{Hmax} in several intervals, which is linked to high modeled stiffness where V_s (and therefore E) is elevated, especially in limestone/dolostone units. The details of the distribution of borehole failure, and particularly BOs, are not very well captured by the 1D MEM, likely due to uncertainty in the strength estimate. In addition, we did not consider the variety of failure modes that can occur at the borehole wall, including failures controlled by local fractures. Such heterogeneities likely have a large local influence on actual borehole failure.

Another discrepancy in the current 1D MEM is that the stress contrast between the Bänkerjoch and Schinznach formations is opposite to that indicated by mini-frac tests. The mini-frac tests indicate that S_{hmin} magnitudes are higher in the Bänkerjoch Fm. The 1D MEM shows, on average, higher stress magnitudes in the Schinznach Fm., which is controlled by the stiffness contrast: the stiffer Schinznach Fm. compared to the Bänkerjoch Fm. should lead to a larger stress magnitude in the Schinznach Fm., but the opposite is measured from mini-frac tests. Potential contrasts in Poisson's ratio also do not provide a satisfactory explanation. We do not fully understand this discrepancy at the moment, although it does not call into question the stress magnitude estimates from the mini-frac tests. However, it highlights the need for (i) better estimation of rock-mechanical parameters (E , ν) from sonic velocities, (ii) accounting for scale effects between laboratory and log-derived properties, and (iii) consideration of local heterogeneity (bedding, stylolites, open or healed fractures), which strongly influences strength and failure. To address the last point, future work could for example treat the Bänkerjoch as a mechanically coupled composite material to derive a more representative effective stiffness and stress magnitudes. It also calls for the application of an iterative stress-characterization approach in which new data are used to update and improve the MEM.

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A. Tracing of data sources

A.1. Source of information

Table 5 provides an overview of the references used to extract the parameters required to create the 1D mechanical earth model (MEM) along the Trüllikon borehole (TRU1-1).

A.1.1. Borehole trajectory

The borehole trajectory (survey) is taken from RD1, Appendix F. The values from the PDF file were copied and slightly edited to create a table in text format, using tab characters as separators.

A.1.2. Borehole diameter

Borehole diameters are taken from RD1, Table 4-3, and arranged in a text file.

A.1.3. Simplified lithostratigraphy

A simplified lithostratigraphy is taken from RD2, Table 1-2, and the information is copied into a tabulated text file.

A.1.4. Stress magnitudes

The stress magnitudes were taken from the micro-hydraulic fracturing (MHF) test results in RD6. The least principal stress magnitude (S_3 , corresponding to S_{hmin} in Trüllikon) is estimated from the closure stress range determined by different methods as detailed in RD6 and RD3. The maximum horizontal stress magnitude (S_{Hmax}) was estimated using the sleeve reopening tests, as also detailed in RD6.

A.1.5. Formation/Pore pressure

The static formation pressure (often also termed pore pressure) is taken from RD4 and arranged in a text file.

A.1.6. Rock-mechanical properties

The Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, and unconfined compressive strength are taken from unconfined compressive strength (UCS) tests and triaxial deformation (TRX) tests, specified in RD5. The data is arranged in a text file.

A. Tracing of data sources

A.1.7. Logging data: density and sonic

The wireline logging data described in RD3 was converted from a .las to a text file. The file contains the borehole azimuth (HAZI), borehole deviation (DEVI), density (RHOZ), compressional wave slowness (DTCO), and shear wave slowness (DTSM) with a depth resolution of 0.1524 m.

A.1.8. Borehole failure

Borehole failure is extracted from Heidbach et al. (2025). The figure of the paper showing the borehole failure in Trüllikon has been digitized. **Borehole breakouts (BOs)** and **drilling induced tensile fractures (DITFs)** are considered. Data were resampled on a regular measured depth scale with a 0.5 m resolution. **BOs** and **DITFs** azimuth as well as **BOs** width are computed. All data are exported in text format (BOs.txt and DITFs.txt).

Table 5: List of **Nagra** reports used in this documentation

ID	Reference	Specific data source
RD1	NAB 20-09 - TBO Trüllikon-1-1 Dossier I: Drilling	Appendix F: Borehole survey Tab 4-3: Borehole sections and diameters
RD2	NAB 20-09 - TBO Trüllikon-1-1 Dossier III: Lithostratigraphy	Tab 1-2: Simplified lithological column
RD3	NAB 20-09 - TBO Trüllikon-1-1 Dossier VI: Wireline Logging and Micro-hydraulic Fracturing	Tab 5-8: Quicklook interpretation of MHF results Appendix E: Raw MHF Pressure-Time and Reconciliation Plots
RD4	NAB 20-09 - TBO Trüllikon-1-1 Dossier VII: Hydraulic Packer Testing	Tab 5-2: Summary of hydraulic packer testing
RD5	NAB 20-09 Rev. 1 - TBO Trüllikon-1-1 Dossier IX: Rock-mechanical and Geomechanical Laboratory Testing	Tab 5-2: UCS test results Tab 5-3, 5-4: Triaxial test results
RD6	NAB 24-19 - In-Situ Stress Field in the Siting Regions Jura Ost, Nördlich Lägern and Zürich Nordost	Whole report and Appendices C.3, D.3, F.3
RD7	NAB 24-10 Rev. 1: Geological Properties of the Jura Ost, Nördlich Lägern and Zürich Nordost Siting Regions for Safety Assessment	Encl. 7: Recommended parameter bandwidths